

UTC-UTI YEAR 4 JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS (4/2020 to 9/2020)

Selected Journal Publications:

01. Alawad, O., Gombeda, M., Quiel, S. and Naito, C. (2020), "Flexural Performance of Non-Loadbearing Blast-Resistant Precast Concrete Cladding Panels with Discrete Connections," *Journal of Building Engineering*, Vol. 32, November 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2020.101438>
02. Drury, Michael M., Amy N. Kordosky, and Spencer E. Quiel (2020). "Structural fire resistance of partially restrained, partially composite floor beams, II: Modeling." *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 167, 105946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2020.105946>
03. Kolay, C., Al-Subaihawi, S., Marullo, T., Ricles, J. and Quiel S. (2020), "Multi-Hazard Real-Time Hybrid Simulation of a Tall Building with Damped Outriggers," *International Journal of Lifecycle Performance Engineering (Inderscience)*, Vol. 4, No. 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJLCPE.2020.108937>
04. Kordosky, A., Drury, M. and Quiel, S. (2020), "Structural Fire Resistance of Partially Restrained, Partially Composite Floor Beams, I: Experiments," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, Vol. 167, April 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2020.105945>
05. Krajnovich, A., Zhou, W. and Gutierrez, M. (2020). "Uncertainty assessment for 3D geologic modeling of fault zones based on geologic inputs and prior knowledge." *Solid Earth*, 11, 1457–1474. <https://doi.org/10.5194/se-11-1457-2020>
06. Lu, M., Sua, L., Gutierrez, M., Zhang, Y., Chen, K. and Zheng, B. (2020), "Verification of Fracture Reorientation and Analysis of Influence Factors in Multiple Fracturing Treatment," *Geofluids*, Article ID 2457814, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2457814>
07. Ma, S. and Gutierrez, M. (2020), "A Time-Dependent Creep Model for Rock Based on Damage Mechanics," *Environmental Earth Sciences*, vol. 79, paper no. 466. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-020-09198-7>
08. Ma, S., Gutierrez, M. and Hou, Z. (2020). "A Coupled Plasticity and Damage Constitutive Model Considering Residual Shear Strength for Shales," *International Journal of Geomechanics*, Vol. 20, No. 8. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GM.1943-5622.0001721](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GM.1943-5622.0001721)
09. Ma, S., Liu, X. and Gutierrez, M. (2020), Critical Issues for the Ground Control of Shallow Roadways in Weak Ground: A Case Study," *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, Vol. 13: 623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-020-05639-6>
10. Nagrecha, Kabir, Luis Fisher, Michael Mooney, Tonatiuh Rodriguez-Nikl, Mehran Mazari, and Mohammad Pourhomayoun. (2020). "As-Encountered Prediction of Tunnel Boring Machine Performance Parameters using Recurrent Neural Networks." *Transportation Research Record* 2674, 10, 241-249. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0361198120934796>
11. Naito, C. (2020) "Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Prestressed Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge," *Case Study, ASCE Bridge Journal*, Vol. 25, No. 7, 05020001. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0001551](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0001551)
12. Oswald, C. and Quiel, S. (2020) "Design of Load-Bearing Precast Concrete Buildings to Resist Progressive Collapse," *PCI Journal*, Vol. 65, No. 5, September 2020. <https://doi.org/10.15554/pcij65.5-01>

13. Ouyang, Z., Carlton, A., Guo, Q., Naito, C. and Quiel, S. (2020), "Blast Vulnerability of Drop Ceilings in Roadway Tunnels," ASCE Journal of Performance of Constructed Facilities, submitted March 2020, Accepted June 2020, Online Sept. 2020, Vol. 34, No. 6. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CF.1943-5509.0001526](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CF.1943-5509.0001526)
14. Shirole, D., Hedayat, A., and Walton, G. (2020). "Illumination of Damage in Intact Rocks by Ultrasonic Transmission-Reflection and Digital Image Correlation," Journal of Geophysical Research-Solid Earth, 125:7. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JB019526>
15. Tomac, I. and Gutierrez, M. (2020). "Micromechanics of Hydraulic Fracturing and Damage in Granite," Granular Matter, 22, pp. 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10035-020-01023-z>
16. Xu, G. and Gutierrez, M., He, C. and Wang, S. (2020), "Modeling of the Effects of Weakness Planes in Rock Masses on the Stability of Tunnels Using an Equivalent Continuum and Damage Model," Acta Geotechnica, Vol. 5, pp. 2277–2304. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11440-020-01087-4>